

Effects of *Moringa oleifera* (Lam.) Plant Parts as Soil Amendment on the Performance of Some Agricultural Crops in a Screenhouse Environment

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ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of moringa leaf blade (MLB), leaf petiole (MLP), seed (MS) and flower (MF) on the performance of amaranth and okra were evaluated in a screen house using 100 kg N/ha and their residual effects were investigated with millet. The experiment was laid in completely randomized design involving amaranth and okra, four moringa amendments and control and replicated five times to give a total of 50 pots. Four amaranths and two okra per pot were evaluated for dry biomass yield at five weeks after sowing (WAS). Residual effects of the amendments were investigated on 30 millets per pot for dry biomass yield at 12 WAS. Data were analysed using ANOVA at 5% probability. Amaranth and okra yield from MLB (0.75 and 1.37 g/plant) and MLP (0.69 and 1.24 g/plant) were significantly higher than MS (0.50 and 1.01 g/plant), MF (0.41 and 0.96 g/plant) and control (0.24 and 0.58 g/plant). Furthermore, yield of millet from residual effect differed significantly in the order of control (0.13 and 0.10 g/plant) < MF (0.19 and 0.17 g/plant) < MS (0.29 and 0.23 g/plant) < MLP (0.36 and 0.31 g/plant) < MLB (0.42 and 0.39 g/plant). Moringa leaf blade and petiole at 100 kg N/ha improved biomass yield of amaranth and okra as well as millet in the first and second cropping respectively.

Keywords: Moringa amendment, Screenhouse, Residual effect, Biomass yield

INTRODUCTION

Environmental implications such as soil acidity and pollution of underground water resulting from the use of chemical fertilisers on tropical soil for crop production are major challenges in sub-Saharan Africa. On the other hand, scarcity and frequent increase in the price of chemical fertilizers have hindered peasant farmers in the tropics not to have access to the fertilizer for crop production (Fagaria, 2012). The proper solution to the constraints of chemical fertilizer in crop production is the use of organic based fertilizer (Akande *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, organic fertilizers such as crop residue and animal manure can help to maintain stability of organic matter in the soil for

long term productivity within the soil environment and it can also help to facilitate water and nutrient for plant use (Fagaria, 2012). *Moringa oleifera* plant parts have been reported by Foidl *et al.*, (2001) as organic fertilizer for producing fruit and leaf vegetables (Foidl *et al.*, 2001).

Moringa oleifera can be propagated from seed and stem – cutting, and biomass produced from moringa planting materials have potential mineral elements (Osumah *et al.*, 2019), which have been reported in improving the nutritional quality of man and animal (Busani *et al.*, 2011). The plant grows in a variety of climate and sub – standard soils (Tagwira,, 2011), but it does not grow well in a cold environment and loses its leaves during winter (Fuglie, 2001). It has become naturalized in the tropical areas of Africa (Tagwira, 2011); and it fits well into Nigeria farming system and could be profitably cultivated as sole cropping and in alley cropping (Osumah *et al.*, 2019). There has been increased interest in cultivating *Moringa oleifera* due to its inherent potential in man, animal and plant nutrition (Fungli, 2001).

Organic fertiliser produced from plant sources decomposed quickly and release their nutrient faster into the soil than commercial organic fertiliser (Morafa, 2007). Hence, this attribute contribute to the performance of moringa plant parts as organic fertiliser in the production of vegetable crops (Foidl *et al.*, 2001). It is evident that residual nutrient elements in soil amended with organic fertiliser enhanced biomass yield and nutrient uptake of sorghum and millet harvested at different week intervals (Abdulraheem *et al.*, 2012). Much work has not been done on the efficacy of moringa plant parts as soil amendment for crop production. However, in depth investigation needs to be done to determine which of the moringa plant parts among moringa (leaf blade, leaf petiole, seed and flower) as soil amendment that could be used as fertiliser for crop production. The objectives of this study are: (i) To evaluate the growth performance, biomass yield and nutrient uptake of amaranth and okra under different powdered moringa plant parts mixed with degraded soil, (ii) To evaluate the residual effect of moringa amendments on biomass

yield and nutrient uptake of millet and (iii) To screen for the best two among moringa leaf blade, moringa petiole, moringa flower and moringa seed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research work was conducted in the screen house of Department of Crop and Horticultural Sciences, University of Ibadan. The soil used for the experiment was a degraded soil collected from Parry Road, University of Ibadan, Nigeria (7° 26' N, 3° 54' E). The soil physical and chemical properties with nutrient contents of powdered moringa plant parts were determined using standard methods (IITA, 1989). The soil was crushed and passed through a 2 mm sieve and filled into five pots of 5 kg size laid in a completely randomised design in five replications. The treatments used were absolute control and powdered forms of moringa leaf blade (9.0 g), leaf petiole (11.9 g), seed (13.7 g) and flower (14.3 g). The quantity of moringa plant parts applied was equivalent to 100 kg N/ha which is the N requirement of the test crops. Each amendment was thoroughly mixed with the soil, watered to 60% field capacity and allowed to equilibrate for 3 days before planting. Amaranth (*Amaranthus caudatus* L.) – Local variety and okra [*Abelmoschus esculentus* (L.) Moench] – Intermediate variety (cross between local and hybrid variety) were planted in the first cropping while millet (var. X Bornu) was planted in the second cropping. In the first cropping, four amaranths and two okra seeds were sowed separately and allowed to grow in each pot for 3, 4 and 5 weeks after sowing (WAS).

Growth parameters were collected on plant height (cm), number of leaves, stem girth (cm) and leaf area (cm²) while biomass yield (fresh and dry in g/plant) and nutrient uptake (g/plant of N, P and K) were determined by standard methods (IITA, 1989) at the end of 5 WAS. Before the commencement of second cropping, air – drying and sieving of the first cropping soil was done while soils under each treatments per replication were bulked together. Thereafter, soil sample was collected from the bulked soil and then analyzed for pH and residual nutrient contents using standard methods (IITA, 1989). In

the second cropping, thirty millet seeds were sowed in each pot at 2 WAS. At 4, 8 and 12 WAS, thirty millet seedlings per pot were cut at 10 cm above soil level for fresh and dry matter yields while nutrient concentration and uptake were determined by standard methods (IITA, 1989). At the end of second cropping, soil in each pot per treatment was sampled and bulked, and thereafter analyzed for pH, N, P and K using standard methods (IITA, 1989). In all cases, data collected were analyzed with analysis of variance (ANOVA) and least significant difference (LSD) was used to detect differences between treatment means at 5% significant level.

RESULTS

Nutrient composition of moringa plant parts

Plant analysis showed that moringa leaf blade had the highest contents of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and magnesium (Mg) than other moringa plant parts while potassium (K) and calcium (Ca) were highest in moringa petiole (Table 1).

Nutrient Status of Degraded Soil used in first Cropping

Table 2 shows the nutrient status of the soil used for first cropping. The value of soil organic matter (10.4 g/kg), N (0.16 g/kg), P (2.1 mg/kg), K (0.05 cmol/kg), Ca (0.6 cmol/kg) and Mg (0.1 cmol/kg) were low when compared with their respective critical levels of 15 – 20 g/kg, 1.2 – 1.5 g/kg, 10 – 15 mg/kg, 0.3 – 0.5, 2 – 2.6 and 0.2 – 0.9 cmol/kg as reported by Uponi and Adeoye (2000). The soil is acidic with pH of 5.1 (Table 2).

Effect of Moringa Amendment on Amaranth and Okra Growth performance

In Table 3 and 4, moringa amendment had significant influence on amaranth and okra plant height, number of leaves and leaf area than control. At 4 and 5 WAS, there was no significant difference between amaranth and okra treated with MLB and MLP in plant height, number of leaves and leaf area. It could be observed that MLB had the highest

amaranth stem girth at 3, 4 and 5 WAS, and it was significantly higher than MF (Table 3).

Effect of Moringa Amendment on Amaranth and Okra Biomass Yield

Amaranth grown with MLB had highest fresh biomass yield, and it was significantly higher than other treatments while amaranth grown with MLP had fresh biomass yield that was significantly higher than amaranth treated with MF and MS (Table 5). However, amaranth grown with MLB produced highest dry matter of 0.75 g/plant and it was significantly higher than 0.41 and 0.50 g/plant obtained from MF and MS respectively. Okra fresh biomass yield obtained from MLB was significantly higher than MS and MF, but it was not significantly higher than MLP. Dry matter produced by okra grown with MLB and MLP were significantly higher than MF, MS and control (Table 5).

Effect of Moringa Amendment on Amaranth and Okra Nutrient Contents and Uptake

Nitrogen, P and K contents in amaranth grown with MLB and MLP were significantly higher than MF and MS (Table 6). In respect to N and K uptake, amaranths grown with MLB and MLP were comparable, and they were significantly higher than control, MS and MF. Amaranth P uptake from MLB was significantly higher than other treatments. Nitrogen, P and K contents of okra grown with MLB and MLP were significantly higher than control, MF and MS. Okra grown with MLB and MLP were comparable in N, P and K uptake and they were significantly higher than N, P and K uptake of okra in control, MF and MS (Table 6).

Nutrient Status of Soil used for Second Cropping

Soil N and organic matter (OM) in amaranth pots treated with powdered moringa leaf blade (MLB) and leaf petiole (MLP) were (1.7 and 1.4 g/kg) and (31.1 and 24.4 g/kg) respectively while that of okra pots were (1.6 and 1.3 g/kg) and (27.2 and 25.7 g/kg) respectively (Table 7). However, N and OM in soils treated with MLB and MLP were within their respective critical levels as reported by Uponi and Adeoye,

(2000). The pH of all moringa amended soils in Table 7 were slightly acidic while P and K in amaranth and okra pots treated with MLB and MLP were significantly higher than control, moringa seed (MS) and moringa flower (MF).

Residual effects of moringa amendment on biomass yield of millet

In Table 8, fresh biomass yield of millet harvested at 4, 8 and 12 WAS from MLB and MLP in pots previously planted to amaranth and okra were comparable and significantly higher than MS and MF. However, the same trend was observed with dry biomass yield of millet at 4, 8 and 12 WAS in pots previously planted to amaranth and okra.

Residual effect of moringa amendment on N, P and K uptake of millet

At 4, 8 and 12 WAS, N uptake of millet observed in MLB and MLP were similar and significantly higher than MS and MF in pots previously planted to amaranth and okra (Table 9). Hence, the same trend was discovered in Millet P and K uptake at 4, 8 and 12 WAS in all pots previously used in experiment 1.

Effect of moringa plant parts on the experimental soil after second cropping

In table 10, soil treated with MLB had highest pH values when compared with MLP, MF and MS. The pH values recorded in pots treated with MLB were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than MF and MS, but it was comparable with the pH values of MLP. From Table 10, it was evident that pots treated with MLB had the highest N and P values, which were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than MLP, MF and MS values. Furthermore, MLP had the highest K values and it was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than MLB, MF and MS. However, K content recorded from pots treated with MLB was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than K contents in pots treated with MF and MS (Table 10).

DISCUSSION

High nutrient elements found in moringa (leaf, petiole, seed and flower) in this study corroborate the reports of Foid *et al.* (2001) and Osumah *et al.* (2019) that moringa plant parts have high macro nutrient elements that can be used as soil amendment for soil fertility improvement. In this study, there is evidence that amaranth, okra and millet respond to soil amended with powdered moringa (leaf blade, leaf petiole, seed and flower), and this was observed on growth, biomass yield and nutrient uptake of the test crops which were significantly higher than control. This research findings confirmed the work of Akande *et al.* (2010) and Abdulraheem *et al.* (2012) who reported that soil amended with organic materials significantly increase okra and sorghum growth components and biomass yield than the control (No fertiliser amendment). The significant effect of moringa plant parts over control in this study is an indication that manure is a store house for various nutrient elements and organic matter which are essential for plant growth (Morafa, 2007). Morafa (2007) further stated that use of organic fertiliser from plant sources on infertile acidic soil can stabilize the soil pH and increase the soil nitrogen content. The statement of Morafa (2007) are in line with the effect of moringa leaf blade and leaf petiole on soil pH stability and high nitrogen content observed in the soil used for second cropping.

However, there are depletion of nutrient elements from soil when use crop like sorghum and millet that are cut and harvested at different weeks interval (Abdulraheem *et al.*, 2012). Nitrogen, P and K depletion were observed in post-cropping chemical analysis of the soil used in this study and they are conformed to the statement of Abdulraheem *et al.* (2012). High nutrient concentration found in the tissue of plant could be as a result of ability of the plant root to efficiently take up nutrient in the soil solution (Osumah *et al.*, 2019). The statement of Osumah *et al.* (2019) justifies the high N, P and K uptake found in amaranth, okra and millet tissues as a result of abundant release of N, P and K from soil treated with moringa leaf blade and leaf petiole. After the second cropping, it is clearly evident from this study that nutrient elements were removed from the soil treated with moringa plant parts

as a result of N, P and K uptake by the test crops, which resulted to N, P and K contents below the critical levels reported by Uponi and Adeoye (2000).

CONCLUSION

Moringa leaf blade and leaf petiole at 100 kg N/ha improved the growth, biomass yield and nutrient uptake of amaranth and okra as well as the performance of millet in residual effects of moringa leaf blade and leaf petiole. Hence, further research findings should be carried out on the field to ascertain the potential of moringa leaf blade and leaf petiole compared with mineral fertiliser.

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Table 1: Nutrient contents of powdered moringa plant parts

Nutrient element	Leaf blade	Leaf Petiole	Flower	Seed
Macronutrient (%)				
Nitrogen	2.79	2.10	1.75	1.82
Phosphorus	0.42	0.28	0.21	0.24
Potassium	1.85	2.06	0.63	0.85
Calcium	1.92	2.23	0.70	1.02
Magnesium	0.19	0.15	0.10	0.13

Table 2: Soil chemical properties and particle size distribution of degraded soil used in first cropping

Soil properties	Values
pH in water (1:1)	5.1
Total nitrogen (g/kg)	0.16
Available phosphorus (mg/kg) Bray p1	2.1
Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg)	
Ca	0.6

Effects of *Moringa oleifera* (Lam.) Plant Parts as Soil Amendment on the Performance of Some Agricultural Crops in a Screenhouse Environment

Mg	0.1
K	0.05
Na	0.1
Organic matter (g/kg)	10.4
Particle size distribution (%)	
Sand	752
Silt	147
Clay	101
Textural class	Sandy loam

Table 3: Effects of moringa amendment on amaranth growth performance

Treatment	Plant height			Number of leaves			Stem girth (cm)			Leaf area (cm ²)
	3	4	5	3	WAS 4	5	3	4	5	5 WAS
Control	11.4	17.5	20.7	7.8	10.3	12.9	0.3	0.5	0.6	20.1
MLB	22.7	30.3	34.6	9.5	14.8	18.7	1.1	1.3	1.5	56.9
MLP	21.2	28.1	33.5	8.9	13.6	18.0	1.0	1.2	1.4	49.7
MF	16.1	23.9	28.8	8.3	12.2	15.1	0.7	1.0	1.2	37.5
MS	17.8	24.6	29.2	8.4	12.5	15.6	0.8	1.1	1.3	38.2
LSD (0.05)	2.7	3.3	3.5	NS	1.4	1.9	0.2	0.2	0.2	12.9

NS: Not significant at $p < 0.05$, WAS: Weeks after sowing, MLB= Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP= Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF=Moringa Flower and MS=Moringa Seed.

Table 4: Effects of moringa amendment on okra growth performance

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Number of leaves			Stem girth(cm)			Leaf area (cm ²)
	3	4	5	3	WAS 4	5	3	4	5	WAS 5
Control	9.7	15.2	23.5	5.0	9.0	11.4	0.8	1.0	1.3	183.1
MLB	14.4	21.5	36.1	6.0	11.7	17.2	1.3	1.5	2.0	324.3
MLP	13.8	21.1	35.3	5.7	11.2	16.5	1.2	1.4	1.9	307.5
MF	12.0	18.9	30.8	5.3	10.0	14.3	0.9	1.1	1.7	255.9
MS	12.6	19.4	31.4	5.4	10.5	14.8	1.0	1.3	1.8	262.8
LSD (0.05)	1.3	2.1	3.6	NS	1.1	1.5	NS	NS	NS	50.7

NS: Not significant at $p < 0.05$, WAS= Weeks After Sowing, MLB= Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP=Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF=Moringa Flower and MS=Moringa Seed

Effects of *Moringa oleifera* (Lam.) Plant Parts as Soil Amendment on the Performance of Some Agricultural Crops in a Screenhouse Environment

Table 5: Effects of moringa amendment on amaranth and okra biomass yield (g/plant)

Treatment	Fresh weight	Dry weight
-Amaranth pots		
Control	3.37	0.24
MLB	8.15	0.75
MLP	6.62	0.69
MF	5.05	0.41
MS	5.31	0.50
LSD (0.05)	1.21	0.14
-Okra pots		
Control	5.01	0.58
MLB	9.98	1.37
MLP	9.25	1.24
MF	7.72	0.96
MS	7.86	1.01
LSD (0.05)	1.25	0.22

MLB=Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP=Moringa Leaf Petiole,
MF=Moringa Flower and MS=Moringa Seed.

Table 6: Effects of moringa amendment on amaranth and okra nutrient contents and uptake

Treatment	Nutrient content (%)			Nutrient uptake (g/plant)		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
-Amaranth pots						
Control	0.89	0.17	0.30	0.21	0.04	0.07
MLB	1.96	0.40	0.68	1.47	0.30	0.51
MLP	1.78	0.35	0.71	1.23	0.24	0.49
MF	1.43	0.26	0.49	0.59	0.11	0.20
MS	1.54	0.28	0.52	0.77	0.14	0.26
LSD (0.05)	0.39	0.09	0.13	0.29	0.05	0.11
-Okra pots						
Control	0.97	0.24	0.52	0.56	0.14	0.30
MLB	3.10	0.65	1.02	4.25	0.89	1.39
MLP	2.93	0.58	0.95	3.63	0.72	1.18
MF	2.34	0.40	0.74	2.24	0.38	0.71
MS	2.45	0.44	0.87	2.47	0.44	0.88
LSD (0.05)	0.63	0.12	0.20	1.06	0.15	0.26

MLB=Moringa Leaf Blade,MLP=Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF= Moringa Flower and MS= Moringa Seed

Effects of *Moringa oleifera* (Lam.) Plant Parts as Soil Amendment on the Performance of Some Agricultural Crops in a Screenhouse Environment

Table 7: Nutrient concentration of soil used for second cropping

Treatment	pH	O.M	N	P	K
	(1:1H ₂ O)	g/kg	(g/kg)	(mg/kg)	(cmol/kg)
-In pots planted to okra in first cropping					
Control	5.4	8.3	0.09	0.8	0.07
MLB	6.5	27.2	1.6	7.2	0.8
MLP	6.3	25.7	1.3	6.5	1.3
MF	6.1	16.9	0.9	3.3	0.2
MS	6.0	18.8	1.0	4.9	0.5
LSD(0.05)	0.5	3.1	0.3	0.7	0.08
-In pots planted to amaranth in first cropping					
Control	5.2	9.2	0.1	1.2	0.1
MLB	6.8	31.1	1.7	8.1	1.1
MLP	6.7	28.4	1.4	7.3	1.5
MF	6.2	17.4	1.1	4.0	0.6
MS	6.0	21.0	1.2	5.6	0.9
LSD(0.05)	0.6	2.8	0.4	0.9	0.09

OM= Organic matter, MLB = Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP =Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF = Moringa Flower and MS =Moringa Seed.

Table 8: Residual effect of moringa amendment on millet biomass yield (g/plant) at different weeks of harvest

Treatments	Fresh weight (g/plant)			Dry weight (g/plant)		
	4	8	12	4	8	12
-Millet planted in amaranth pots used in first cropping						
Control	1.02	0.90	0.66	0.19	0.17	0.13
MLB	2.14	1.8	1.75	0.55	0.49	0.42
MLP	1.94	1.73	1.61	0.48	0.41	0.36
MF	1.42	1.30	1.22	0.31	0.25	0.19
MS	1.56	1.41	1.34	0.37	0.32	0.27
LSD(0.05)	0.18	0.07	0.10	0.03	0.05	0.02
-Millet planted in okra pots used in first cropping						
Control	0.95	0.81	0.52	0.16	0.14	0.10
MLB	2.09	1.79	1.63	0.50	0.44	0.39
MLP	1.86	1.62	1.55	0.43	0.38	0.31
MF	1.39	1.27	1.18	0.29	0.21	0.17
MS	1.48	1.36	1.25	0.35	0.28	0.23
LSD(0.05)	0.22	0.15	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.01

WAS = Weeks After Sowing, MLB = Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP = Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF = Moringa Flower and MS =Moringa Seed.

Table 9: Residual effect of moringa amendment on millet nutrient concentration (% dry matter) and uptake (g/plant) at 4, 8 and 12 WAS

Treatments	Nutrient Concentration (%)			Nutrient Uptake (g/plant)		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
-Millet planted in amaranth pots used in first cropping (Harvested at 4 WAS)						
Control	0.63	0.17	0.39	0.12	0.03	0.07
MLB	1.94	0.60	0.91	1.07	0.33	0.50
MLP	1.80	0.53	0.78	0.86	0.25	0.37
MF	1.39	0.37	0.50	0.43	0.11	0.16
MS	1.56	0.40	0.64	0.58	0.15	0.24
LSD(0.05)	0.13	0.05	0.07	0.10	0.03	0.04
-Millet planted in okra pots used in first cropping						
Control	0.45	0.13	0.22	0.07	0.02	0.04
MLB	1.61	0.51	0.83	0.81	0.26	0.41
MLP	1.49	0.46	0.71	0.64	0.20	0.31
MF	1.07	0.28	0.42	0.31	0.08	0.12
MS	1.22	0.33	0.58	0.43	0.11	0.20
LSD(0.05)	0.11	0.04	0.09	0.07	0.02	0.03
-Millet planted in amaranth pots used in first cropping (Harvested at 8 WAS)						
Control	0.38	0.15	0.24	0.06	0.02	0.04
MLB	1.52	0.57	0.80	0.74	0.28	0.39
MLP	1.41	0.49	0.69	0.58	0.20	0.28
MF	0.75	0.29	0.41	0.19	0.07	0.10
MS	0.10	0.35	0.57	0.03	0.11	0.18
LSD(0.05)	0.11	0.05	0.09	0.07	0.02	0.03
-Millet planted in okra pots used in first cropping						
Control	0.26	0.10	0.18	0.04	0.01	0.03
MLB	1.34	0.44	0.65	0.59	0.19	0.29
MLP	1.19	0.39	0.57	0.45	0.15	0.22
MF	0.60	0.23	0.36	0.13	0.05	0.08
MS	0.81	0.27	0.46	0.23	0.08	0.13
LSD(0.05)	0.10	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.02
-Millet planted in amaranth pots used in first cropping (Harvested at 12 WAS)						
Control	0.32	0.08	0.16	0.04	0.01	0.02
MLB	1.37	0.36	0.67	0.58	0.15	0.28
MLP	1.29	0.31	0.60	0.46	0.11	0.21
MF	0.53	0.18	0.30	0.10	0.03	0.06
MS	0.91	0.22	0.49	0.24	0.05	0.11
LSD(0.05)	0.08	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.02
-Millet planted in okra pots used in first cropping						
Control	0.17	0.05	0.11	0.02	0.01	0.01

Effects of *Moringa oleifera* (Lam.) Plant Parts as Soil Amendment on the Performance of Some Agricultural Crops in a Screenhouse Environment

MLB	1.21	0.30	0.53	0.47	0.12	0.20
MLP	1.05	0.26	0.45	0.36	0.08	0.14
MF	0.47	0.16	0.27	0.08	0.03	0.05
MS	0.66	0.20	0.35	0.15	0.04	0.08
LSD(0.05)	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.01

WAS = Weeks After Sowing, MLB = Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP = Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF = Moringa Flower and MS = Moringa Seed.

Table 10: Post-cropping chemical analysis on the experimental soil

Treatment	pH	N	P	K
	(1:1H ₂ O)	(g/kg)	(mg/kg)	(cmol/kg)
-Millet planted in okra pots				
Control	4.3	0.01	0.06	0.01
MLB	5.9	0.5	1.7	0.11
MLP	5.6	0.3	1.2	0.16
MF	5.3	0.06	0.5	0.04
MS	5.1	0.08	0.6	0.05
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.04	0.1	0.02
-Millet planted in amaranth pots				
Control	4.0	0.03	0.09	0.02
MLB	5.6	0.8	2.0	0.14
MLP	5.5	0.4	1.6	0.20
MF	5.2	0.1	0.8	0.07
MS	5.0	0.1	1.0	0.08
LSD(0.05)	0.3	0.06	0.2	0.03

MLB= Moringa Leaf Blade, MLP= Moringa Leaf Petiole, MF= Moringa Flower and MS= Moringa Seed